

to share some files in a PDF, but others only on DVD. Other archives may have more restrictive policies on data sharing.

These challenges notwithstanding, as this piece has discussed, there are important reasons to adopt

annotation as a research practice: Annotations increase the quality of research by increasing its transparency and reproducibility as well as the strength of both descriptive and causal inference.

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Upgrading an Old QCA Study to Make it More Transparent and Reproducible Using R Markdown

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In 2006, an article on the causes of resignations and non-resignations of federal ministers in Germany was published, which included one of us, Ingo, as one of three co-authors (Fischer, Kaiser, and Rohlfing 2006). As part of the empirical analysis, the article uses Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) to derive the conditions under which ministers who are under pressure to resign do resign or stay in office. In this contribution to the symposium, we explain why we returned to the original QCA analysis after more than 15 years and how we enhanced its transparency and reproducibility by redoing it using R Markdown.¹

We begin with a brief summary of the QCA workflow. We use a simple template of the workflow for a discussion of how it was implemented in the QCA analysis of ministerial resignations. This will show that a mix of several elements motivates a reproduction

analysis after more than 15 years. First, the original QCA study is transparent in large part, but it is not as transparent as we now think that it should have been. The reanalysis allows us to enhance the transparency of the entire workflow and analysis. Second, the original analysis was implemented with the QCA 3.0 software using a graphical user interface (GUI). A graphical user interface notoriously impedes the opportunity to render a QCA study transparent and reproducible because one has to manually edit the data and intervene in the analysis. This accounts for our decision to reproduce the original study in an R Markdown framework. The reproduction analysis is code-based and allows us to produce a report that combines the code with the reporting of the results. In section three, we explain that the original results can be reproduced using R Markdown and how exactly this allows us to improve upon the original GUI-based study.

¹ We define a study as reproducible when one is able to derive the same results as in the original study when using the same data and following the same procedure as it is documented in the original study.

The final section concludes with a short discussion of the pros and cons of using R Markdown for QCA research, where we argue that the pros outweigh the cons.

The QCA Workflow and the Analysis of Ministerial Resignations in Germany: What Was Done and What Could Have Been Done Better

The original QCA study is based on a dataset of 111 debates about federal ministers in Germany resigning from office.² The outcome of interest is whether a minister finally resigned (positive outcome) or not (negative outcome of non-resignation). The goal was to determine the conditions under which a minister resigns or stays in office. As part of the analysis, we ran a QCA study that derived the conditions of resignation and non-resignation from 111 cases of debates about resignations of federal ministers in Germany from 1969-2005.³

The main finding of the QCA study was that a minister resigns if one of five constellations applies: the minister wants to resign (happened once); the minister's party demands resignation; the trigger of the resignation debate preceded the minister taking office and the issue is political; the chancellor and the opposition demand

resignation; or the reason for resignation precedes the entry into office, there was no judicial investigation, and the opposition opposes resignation. We do not want to go further into the details of the theory and empirical substance here and instead focus on those elements of the QCA workflow that are generic to the set-relational analysis (for a broader view see Schneider, Vis, and Koivu 2019; Schneider and Wagemann 2010; Wagemann and Schneider 2016). From this perspective, one can distinguish four steps of the analysis: (1) calibration, that is, the transformation of variables into sets; (2) the creation of a truth table based on the set-relational data; (3) the derivation of prime implicants from the truth table through a minimization process;⁴ and (4) the construction of minimal *models* based on the prime implicants derived in step 3.⁵ Each of the steps requires researchers to make analytical choices that need to be transparent. We summarize these decisions in Table 1, alongside information about how the decisions were made in the analysis of ministerial resignations.

Table 1. Example QCA Workflow and Implementation

Stage of the workflow	Design choices	Original study
Calibration	Type of set (crisp, multivalued, fuzzy)	Crisp sets
	Calibration strategy (informal; formalized using link functions)	Informal calibration based on case knowledge
Generation of truth table	Management of contradictions	Case-based discussion of contradictions and resolution of contradictions
Derivation of prime implicants	Decision about sufficiency of truth table rows without cases (i.e., remainders; conservative or parsimonious approach)	Parsimonious approach <i>Issue:</i> Remainders that are assumed to be sufficient not reported
Derivation of solutions	How many and what solutions to report under model ambiguity	No model ambiguity for ministerial resignations reported for original analysis Model ambiguity for non-resignations stated in article <i>Issue:</i> Only one model shown; total number of models not mentioned

² The data was collected by Jörn Fischer, who put in tremendous effort.

³ Ingo was in charge of the QCA study.

⁴ A prime implicant is a superset of a truth table row that is derived through the minimization of a row.

⁵ An additional step that one could integrate is the analysis of necessary relationships between the conditions and the outcome. This is not required for the generation of QCA solutions and was not done in the analysis of ministerial resignations.

The first two stages of the QCA workflow are transparently implemented in the original analysis. It works with crisp sets, that is a case is either a member of a set or a non-member. In stage 1 of the workflow, all sets had been calibrated qualitatively and informally based on case knowledge.⁶

In stage 2, at the time the crisp-set QCA study was conducted, each truth table row had to be either sufficient for the presence of the outcome or its negation. One could only produce a truth table when all rows were free of contradictions, where a “contradiction” is defined by the presence of at least two cases that are members of the same truth table row but that display different membership in the outcome (Ragin 1987, chapter 7).⁷ In the original analysis, one truth table row is a contradiction with 24 cases of non-resignation and two cases of resignation within the configuration. A case-based approach was followed by a discussion of the two resignation cases. It was decided that they displayed singular characteristics and could be dropped from the analysis. This process is transparently described in the article (Fischer, Kaiser, and Rohlfing 2006, 727).

In step 3 of the analysis, the processed truth table was minimized to derive the prime implicants. At the time of the analysis, the conservative (i.e., complex) approach and the parsimonious approach were available. We opted for the parsimonious solution (Fischer, Kaiser, and Rohlfing 2006, 734), which makes assumptions about the sufficiency of remainders for the outcome such that the maximum degree of minimization and simplicity of the final model is achieved (Ragin 1987, chapter 6). While it is transparent that the parsimonious approach is followed, it is not reported what truth table rows without cases were assumed to be sufficient in the minimization processes. This should have been made transparent because the assumptions about remainders are crucial and the reader must be put in a position to evaluate these assumptions.

In step 4, one builds a minimal solution based on the prime implicants such that each truth table row that is sufficient for the outcome is represented by (or covered) by at least one prime implicant. Stages 3 and 4 of the QCA workflow were not clearly distinguished until the phenomenon of *model ambiguity* gained attention in recent years (Baumgartner and Thiem 2017; Thiem 2014, 498–

500). Model ambiguity denotes a situation in which it is possible to represent the truth table rows through more than one combination (disjunction) of prime implicants. The original analysis of ministerial resignations, which was the outcome of prime interest, produced only one model. The analysis of non-resignations yielded model ambiguity (Fischer, Kaiser, and Rohlfing 2006, 734). The original analysis makes transparent which prime implicants were chosen to produce the solution for non-resignations. However, it would have been better to report all models that had been derived for non-resignations because their substantive interpretation differs, and because each model could be the correct one (assuming the results can be interpreted causally) (Baumgartner and Thiem 2017).

All these reasons are related to the goal of making the analysis more transparent and add more information to the reporting of the results. In addition, there are *software-related reasons* that call for a reanalysis.

Software-Related Reasons for a Reanalysis

The software-related reasons are tied to the fact that QCA 3.0 had a graphical user interface (GUI). First, we could not share a script with code for the original analysis that enhances transparency about analysis decisions.⁸ Second, when one faces model ambiguity in a GUI-based analysis, one has to select prime implicants to derive a single model. If model ambiguity is extensive, the manual selection process of prime implications is tedious. One has to do it for each of the models individually, and it is possible that one overlooks one model when selecting the implicants. Third, we explained above that one truth table row is a contradiction in the original analysis. Whatever the approach is towards the resolution of contradictions (Ragin 1987, chapter 7), it required the *manual* editing of the unprocessed dataset either by recoding sets of cases on the conditions or outcome or by removing them from the dataset. This means one dataset was needed to produce the truth table with a contradiction and one processed dataset was needed to have a contradiction-free truth table that can be minimized. Fourth, the original analysis reports descriptive statistics such as the number of truth table rows. This information had to be derived manually

⁶ The outcome set is the formal resignation of a minister; the negation is the non-resignation. The condition sets are the position for or against resignation by the minister; the chancellor of Germany; their own party; the coalition partner; the opposition parties; the public and media; and the minister. Additional sets include: whether the issue that initiated the resignation was political or personal; whether the debate about resignation started before the minister assumed or had taken office; and whether judicial investigations into the issue that started the debate.

⁷ A simplified example for a contradiction could be the two resignation debates in which the German chancellor was in favor of resignation, but where the minister resigned only in one of the two cases.

⁸ The only direct way to document a GUI-based analysis is to screencast it. Ingo had not even remotely considered this previously, and it is, to our knowledge, rarely done at present in empirical research.

from the data and GUI-based analysis. Fifth, even if we accepted all these constraints of a GUI-based analysis, a practical problem would remain. To our knowledge, the QCA 3.0 software is not publicly available anymore to rerun the original analysis and remedy the issues that we discussed above.

Reproducing the Original Analysis Using R Markdown

The reproduction analysis uses the QCA package (Dusa 2019) for R (R Core Team 2020) in combination with R Markdown (Xie, Dervieux, and Riederer 2020). The use of the QCA package in an R Markdown framework allows us to address all the elements that we discussed before. The QCA package allows us to establish full transparency about the entire workflow and analysis decisions. It also makes it easy to extract descriptive statistics about the truth table. The use of a script instead of a GUI enhances transparency intrinsically because all analysis choices are documented by the code. However, a script does not improve transparency about the results because they are displayed in a results window.⁹ In a purely script-based analysis one would also need to screencast the analysis to fully document it and the results.

The QCA study in an R Markdown framework remedies this problem because it produces an *R Markdown report*. An R Markdown file includes plain text (documentation, annotations, etc.) and chunks with code that is the same as in a plain R script. The advantage of an R Markdown file is its dynamic nature, because its execution combines code and results in an html-file, Word file, PDF, or another format (Xie, Dervieux, and Riederer 2020). This feature of R Markdown is invaluable for transparency and reproducibility because it directly ties results to code. It also does not require any manual editing of the data in the workflow.

With regard to the congruence of the results in the original study and the reproduction analysis, we can *confirm* all results of the original analysis. This includes the truth table with a contradictory row; the creation of a contradiction-free truth table by removing the two cases; and the reproduction of the models for resignations and non-resignations that are reported in the article. The realization of the QCA study using R Markdown allows us to improve upon the original analysis in the following ways.

First, we can remove the two cases from the contradictory truth table row during the analysis with code, which means we do not have to work with two

separate datasets. Second, we can derive and show the prime implicants that account for model ambiguity for non-resignations and all twelve models that can be derived from the truth table. Furthermore, R Markdown allows us to present all 16 models in the final report as opposed to manually performing 16 minimizations using a GUI.¹⁰ Third, we report the truth table rows without cases that have been assumed to be sufficient for resignations and non-resignations in the respective minimization processes. This, in turn, allows us to check for contradictory assumptions about remainders without comparing the assumptions by hand. The code-based check for contradictory assumptions confirms the statement in the original analysis that none have been made in the empirical analysis (Fischer, Kaiser, and Rohlfing 2006, 734). Fifth, we can easily report descriptive statistics for the set-relational data and the truth table, such as the total number of rows with cases, the number of rows that are sufficient for resignations, etc. Since the value of R Markdown lies in the production of an analysis report, we invite the reader to visit the repository for the reproduction analysis and to take a look at the R Markdown file and the report that it creates (Rohlfing and Bekmuratovna R. 2021).

5. Conclusion

In our contribution, we reported our motivation for returning to a QCA study from more than 15 years ago to enhance its transparency and verify that it is reproducible. What do we learn from the reanalysis and what does this analysis imply for QCA research and qualitative research more generally?

From the viewpoint of reproducibility, it is positive that we could fully reproduce the original results and confirm that no mistakes had been made in the original analysis, which required multiple manual interventions in the process and data. It might then seem futile to do such a reanalysis, but this would be a false conclusion for two reasons. First, this is a hindsight evaluation of reproduction studies and misses that one does not know whether an original analysis is reproducible until one has done it. Second, from a personal point of view (as Ingo was involved in the original study), it is good to dispel any lingering doubt about whether everything had been done correctly in the GUI-based analysis and to have it now documented transparently.

This point hints at the clear advantages to the realization of a QCA study in R compared to GUI software. An R script increases transparency and relieves

⁹ This is the console or graph tab in RStudio (RStudio Team 2021).

¹⁰ We cannot determine whether the same 16 models could have been produced with QCA 3.0 because the software is not available anymore. Since the solution for resignations is the same as in the original analysis, we believe that the 16 models for non-resignations are those that could have been previously derived with QCA 3.0.

empirical researchers from manually performing the same steps again and again when using GUI software. The realization of the QCA study in R using R Markdown obviously comes at the cost of learning how to code in R, but there are several excellent resources available for getting started with R and R Markdown (Dusa 2019; Xie, Dervieux, and Riederer 2020; Oana, Schneider, and Thomann 2021).

In the context of this symposium, a broader issue concerns the idea and role of “transparency” and “reproducibility” beyond the standardized elements of QCA research. We believe the idea of “transparency” should be a common denominator for all kinds of empirical research, the main question being how to achieve it (Kapiszewski and Karcher 2021). QCA research using R makes it relatively easy to be transparent and achieve reproducibility because it is based on code that can be shared. This element of QCA research does not generalize because other forms of qualitative research—process tracing using primary and secondary sources, discourse analysis, etc.—do not involve code.

Still, we believe there are two broader lessons of this reproduction study. First, one should use software whenever possible. In non-QCA research, this could for example be computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS) such as Nvivo or Atlas.ti. This software allows one to systemize the collection and management of all types of sources, print, video, and audio, as well as the analysis of the sources and the reporting of results. Second, as a complement to CAQDAS and even more so when it is not used, one should consider the use of a *research diary* (or open notebook) documenting in real time every step of the analysis and the decisions that have been made (Bloor and Wood 2006, 151-3).¹¹ A diary could also be useful for code-based QCA research because it can be equally interesting to document why certain decisions have *not* been made. With these two general tools—software with or without code—and a meticulous documentation of the process, we believe that transparency of different types of qualitative research can be enhanced.¹²

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11 One can conceive of this as the equivalent to an open notebook in code-based research.

12 The question of whether reproducibility follows from transparency is an epistemological question that we cannot cover in detail here (Jacobs et al. 2021). For the standardized parts of QCA, it is clear that it should be reproducible.

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Transparency in Case Studies: Methodological Appendices

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When writing qualitative case study research, most of us find that the very stuff of analysis—that is, the qualitative data—is lengthy and nuanced. Additionally, qualitative methods are often used in situations where “theories are underdeveloped and concepts are vague” (Ragin, Berg-Schlosser, and de Meur 1998, 750). To be robust and compelling, the data we use may require lengthy explanation, precisely because we wish to capture complexity. Overall, qualitative research relies on words—often lots of them—to get our point across.

Moreover, induction is often key to the sorts of insights that qualitative researchers are poised to offer (Bendassolli 2013). We gather data to form new hypotheses and explanations—a process that can be crucial to “gain[ing] inferential leverage over different questions” (Yom 2015, 618). However, inductive reasoning requires moving from observed data to abstract concepts in ways that cannot be fully deduced from initial premises or hypotheses (Bendassolli 2013, 2). Therefore, the transparency goal of clearly “linking evidence to inference” (Bennett, Fairfield, and Soifer 2019, 2) can be particularly challenging to achieve. Forming propositions or generalizations in qualitative research will often involve choosing one interpretation over others when it comes to data and to the vaguer aspects of the theories and concepts with which we are engaging. The fact that qualitative researchers often make these sorts of choices leaves space for particular kinds of questions to emerge on the reader’s part about how we have arrived at our conclusions.

This contribution focuses on how my coauthors, Sara Casella Colombeau and Elisabeth Badenhoop, and I used a particular tool—a methodological appendix—to explicitly address some of the concerns that qualitative data and the inductive process in general can raise in the more constrained space of an article-length text. The research and appendix were recently published in *Comparative Political Studies* (Slaven, Casella Colombeau, and Badenhoop 2021). A methodological appendix can be defined simply as supplementary (in this case, online-only) material that provides greater detail and specification of the methodological approach than the traditional format of a qualitative research article would allow. We created the methodological appendix thanks to the encouragement and suggestions from others (see below). In conveying our positive experience here, we hope to inspire others to consider it as an arrow in one’s quiver for bolstering transparency in qualitative research.

The Project

We arrived at creating a methodological appendix for this article relatively late in the process of writing the article (and in retrospect, perhaps a little later than ideal, as discussed below). Indeed, it is important to situate writing a methodological appendix as only part of the longer work process of bringing an article to publication.

The three of us had worked on a comparative project that was fully centered on gathering and analyzing qualitative process-tracing data about policy deliberations surrounding immigration policy. The data were collected through a combination of archival research and elite interviews, which we performed